

A DIFFERENTIAL GAME OF ℓ -CATCH UNDER EXPONENTIAL DECREASING CONSTRAINT IN TERMS OF ACCELERATION

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Theory of Differential Games looks into conflict problems in systems which are expressed by differential equations. As a result of the growth of Pontryagin's maximum principle, it became apparent that there was a link between optimal control theory and differential games. Actually, problems of differential game describe a generalization of optimal control problems in cases where there are more than one player.

The study of differential games was initiated by American mathematician R.Isaacs. His research was published in the form of a monograph [5, p. 340] in 1965, in which a great number of examples were considered, and theoretical questions were only affected. Differential games have been one of the basic research fields since the 1960th and their fundamental results were gained by L.S.Pontryagin [9, p. 551], N.N.Krasovsky [3, p. 520]

The problem for the case of ℓ -approach [8, p. 272] was first studied by Indian mathematician Ramchundra. Analogous effects in the case of geometrical constraint were considered in the works of Pshenichnyi [10, p. 484], Chikrii [3, p. 56], Petrosjan [11, p. 140], Satimov [12, p. 26], Grigorenko [4, p. 20], Azamov [1, p. 38], Azamov and Samatov[2, p. 33], Samatov [13], Khaidarov [7, p. 574].

In this paper, we investigate ℓ -catch problem for a differential game of two players, a pursuer and an evader, in an inertial motion with exponential with decreasing constraints in terms of acceleration. We suggest an approach strategy, which is based on the method of resolving function, for a pursuer and by means of the strategy, new sufficient conditions of ℓ -catch are defined.

Consider two players, a pursuer P and an evader E, moving in the space $\square^n$. Suppose that x and y are the locations of the pursuer and the evader respectively.

Let movements of the pursuer and the evader be expressed by the differential equations and initial conditions

$$\ddot{x} = u, \quad x(0) = x_0, \quad \dot{x}(0) = x_1, \quad (1)$$

$$\ddot{y} = v, \quad y(0) = y_0, \quad \dot{y}(0) = y_1, \quad (2)$$

correspondingly, where $x, y, u, v \in \mathbb{R}^n$, $n \geq 2$; x_0, y_0 are the initial locations of the players in which it is supposed that $|x_0 - y_0| > \ell, \ell > 0$; x_1, y_1 are their initial velocity vectors accordingly; the acceleration vectors u, v serve as control parameters of the players respectively, and they varies in respect to the time $t \geq 0$.

The controls u and v will be picked as Lebesgue measurable functions $u(\cdot): [0, +\infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ and $v(\cdot): [0, +\infty) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$ accordingly. We represent by U_ℓ a set off all the measurable functions $u(\cdot)$ such that fulfill the geometric constraints (briefly, G-constraint)

$$|u(t)| \leq \alpha e^{-kt} \quad \text{for almost every } t \geq 0 \quad (3)$$

where $\alpha > 0, k > 0$.

In the same way, we indicate by V_ℓ a set of all the measurable functions $v(\cdot)$ fulfilling the G-constraint

$$|v(t)| \leq \beta e^{-kt} \quad \text{for almost every } t \geq 0 \quad (4)$$

where $\beta > 0, k > 0$.

If $u(\cdot) \in U_\ell$ and $v(\cdot) \in V_\ell$, then by virtue of the equations (1), (2), the triplets $(x_0, x_1, u(\cdot)), (y_0, y_1, v(\cdot))$ define the motion trajectories

$$x(t) = x_0 + x_1 t + \int_0^t (t-s)u(s)ds, \quad (5)$$

$$y(t) = y_0 + y_1 t + \int_0^t (t-s)v(s)ds, \quad (6)$$

of the players correspondingly.

Definition 3.4.1. The measurable function $u(\cdot) \in U_\ell (v(\cdot) \in V_\ell)$ is called an admissible control of player P (of player E).

Note that the pair (U_ℓ, V_ℓ) of the introduced classes defines a differential game.

That the main target of the pursuer is to approach the evader at the range at $\ell > 0$ (ℓ -catch problem), that is, to reach the inequality

$$|x(\eta) - y(\eta)| \leq \ell \quad (7)$$

for some $\eta > 0$. But the basic target of the evader is to prevent occurring the above mentioned inequality, i.e. to keep the relation (evasion problem) $|x(t) - y(t)| > \ell$ for all $t, t \geq 0$, and if it is impossible, the evader strives to delay the instant of ℓ -catch.

Let's introduce the following denotations:

$$z(t) = x(t) - y(t), z_0 = x_0 - y_0, \dot{z}(0) = x_1 - y_1.$$

Then the equation (1), (2) come to the unique Cauchy's problem in the form

$$\ddot{z} = u - v, \quad z(0) = z_0, \quad \dot{z}(0) = z_1. \quad (8)$$

Note that we will consider the differential game (1)-(4) for the case $z_1 = mz_0, m \in \mathbb{R}$

Definition 3.4.2. For $\alpha \geq \beta$, we say the function

$$u(t, v) = v - \lambda(z_0, v) \frac{\alpha e^{-kt} z_0 + v\ell}{\alpha e^{-kt} + \lambda(t, v)\ell} \quad (9)$$

an approach strategy or Π_ℓ -strategy of the player P in the differential game (1)-(4) of ℓ -catch, where, $h^2 = |z_0|^2 - \ell^2$,

$$\lambda(t, v) = \frac{1}{h^2} \left[\langle v, z_0 \rangle + \alpha e^{-kt} \ell + \sqrt{\left(\langle v, z_0 \rangle + \alpha e^{-kt} \ell \right)^2 + h^2 \left(\alpha^2 e^{-2kt} \ell^2 - |v|^2 \right)} \right],$$

and $\langle v, z_0 \rangle$ is the scalar product of the vectors v and z_0 in $\mathbb{R}^n$. Moreover, the function $\lambda(z_0, v)$ is generally titled the resolving function.

Theorem 3.4.1. Let one of the conditions

$$\alpha > \beta, \quad m < \frac{k(\alpha - \beta)^2}{k^2(\alpha|z_0| - \beta\ell) + (\alpha - \beta)\beta};$$

$$\alpha = \beta, \quad m < 0$$

be satisfied. Then the strategy (9) guarantees to occur the relation (7) on the interval $[0, T_\ell]$ in the ℓ -catch problem (1)-(4), where T_ℓ is a guaranteed approach time and it is the first positive root of the equation

$$e^{-kt} = -akt + b, b = 1 + \frac{k^2(|z_0| - \ell)}{\alpha - \beta}, a = 1 - \frac{|z_0|mk}{\alpha - \beta}$$

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